

IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF RUSSIAN LANGUAGE LEARNING BY USING MODERN MEANS OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: the article reveals the relevance of using information technology in a modern Russian language lesson. Specific methods, skills, programs and their positive impact for strengthening the acquired knowledge are also outlined.

Key words: the Russian language, information and communication technologies (ICT), information, design technologies, research technologies, communication skills.

INTRODUCTION

Today we are at the stage of updating the entire education system, introducing new information technologies into the educational process. The latest computer technologies, which have so rapidly burst into our lives, are a powerful tool for obtaining a wide variety of information. In the field of education, they have become an effective means of implementing the principles of clarity, accessibility, systematicity and consistency, scientific character, and have increased interest in learning. In modern conditions of mass computerization and informatization of all aspects of social life, the education system faces new challenges that require finding ways to intensify the learning process and innovative methods of managing it.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The priority for the development of education is the introduction of modern information and communication technologies that ensure the improvement of the educational process, the accessibility and effectiveness of education, and the preparation of the younger generation for life in the information society.

Informatization of education is one of the main directions of the informatization process, dictated by the needs of modern society, in which the main engine of progress is individual development. It should ensure the introduction into practice of program and pedagogical developments aimed at

intensifying the educational process, improving the forms and methods of organizing training.

The main goal of all innovations in the field of education is to promote the transition from students' mechanical acquisition of knowledge to the formation of skills and abilities to independently acquire knowledge. The success of solving this problem largely depends on the purpose of using a computer in the educational process, the quality and capabilities of the software, and on what place the computer will take in the system of teaching tools.

The introduction of information and communication technologies into the educational process is not a tribute to fashion, but a necessity of today, since most children become familiar with a computer much earlier than school can offer them. The need for widespread use of electronic learning tools in the study of any subject is no longer news to anyone.

The introduction of ICT into the educational process is an urgent need of today. The relevance of this issue determined the choice of the topic of the article: "The use of information technology in a modern Russian language lesson as a means of increasing the cognitive activity of students."

The main didactic functions implemented with the help of ICT in Russian language lessons are:

- educational (using computer technology and the Internet, you can obtain any necessary information, both stored on the hard drive of your own computer database and located on CD-ROM drives or corresponding Internet pages);

- developmental (working with a variety of computer programs, in addition to activating the literary capabilities of the individual, contributes to the development of such necessary cognitive processes as perception, logical thinking, memory, imagination);

- research (schoolchildren have the opportunity to participate in literary search groups, Internet competitions; perform creative work of various types, create their own creative projects, develop reports, abstracts, student presentations, publications, research certain problematic issues);

- communicative (when exchanging information between students, a certain virtual unity is created, everyone has a real opportunity to enter the websites of popular contemporary artists; they have the opportunity to compare different views, evaluate them, and form their own positions).

Information technologies are becoming a powerful multifunctional learning tool. Their use accustoms students to live in an information environment and helps to familiarize schoolchildren with information culture.

Conducting a lesson in a computer science classroom allows all students to be involved in processing information at the stage of learning new material. Students are asked to structure the educational material in a form convenient for them: plan, abstract, table, diagram. In addition, the following method is used. At the final stage of the lesson, a group of students creates a small presentation (using a laptop) in which they present a summary of the lesson material. As an example, we can cite the preparation of presentation materials for literature lessons when studying the works of writers of the 19th and 20th centuries, extracurricular activities, preparation of abstracts and research papers for school intellectual readings “Biography of Science in Persons”, for scientific and practical conferences and competitions of various levels . The transmission of information plays an important role in the formation of communicative competence. Complex methods - drawing up and defending an abstract (project), including drawing up a plan, conclusions, bibliography, participation in educational projects with their subsequent interpretation and public presentation of the results, educational research work, publication of student media. A big role in this case is played by the forms of conducting a lesson in the Russian language or literature: lesson-conference, lesson-research, lesson-travel. One of the tasks implemented in these classes is the development of a research type of thinking in schoolchildren. Types of activities that develop students’ research skills:

- studying literature on the topic, analyzing the information received (bibliography, abstracting, citing);
- research planning (setting goals and objectives, choosing research methods, predicting results);
- conducting research (observation, conducting an experiment, recording the results, comparing the results with the planned);
- registration and defense of research results (preparing a report, writing an article, research work, defending the results in front of an audience).

Undoubtedly, it is impossible to use all types of research activities in one lesson. The formation of research skills occurs in stages. And here it seems important to take an active approach to teaching, the use of heuristic methods, when the student, observing the language material, himself formulates a rule or draws conclusions about the idea of a work of art. Knowledge obtained in this way becomes the most valuable. The use of creative tasks in the classroom, searching for answers to problematic questions, working with additional literature, and reasoned defense of one’s point of view also help to develop

research skills. Undoubtedly, two or three hours a year is not enough to turn schoolchildren into speakers, but this is enough to form in them a basic understanding of rhetoric, the requirements for public speaking, the ability to determine a goal, select material, evidence, work on language, answer questions, argue, analyze the performances of comrades. In the first lesson “Public speaking-appeal. Its structure, linguistic features”, sixth-graders get acquainted with the theoretical aspects of the topic, analyze the “speaker’s memo”, the outline of the review of the speech, and perform breathing exercises. For the second lesson, children are preparing a presentation of folk crafts. Their task is to present to the audience the features of the products of folk craftsmen, the principle of creating these products.

Performance indicators can include student achievements:

- students’ acquisition of experience in creative, project, and research activities (i.e., readiness to find solutions to new problems, independent transfer of knowledge and skills to a new situation);
- creation of an individual portfolio of students based on the results of participation in competitions and conferences;
- increasing interest in the subject;
- Consistently high quality of knowledge on the subject;
- 100% academic success;
- successful passing of exams;
- participation and victories in competitions at various levels from school to federal;
- admission of graduates to humanities majors based on the results of the final stage of the All-Russian Olympiad for schoolchildren. And also the demand for experience by teachers of a school, city, region (conducting master classes, open lessons, speaking at seminars).

CONCLUSION

The study of new material offered by a computer program takes on a personality-oriented orientation. In the process of working with educational systems, the process of correcting and updating students’ knowledge has significantly intensified; much less time is spent on these stages of the lesson. Using a computer in the classroom expands my capabilities as a teacher when selecting material for a lesson and forms of educational work, makes the lessons bright and interesting, informationally and emotionally rich.

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